

Article

Towards Sustainable Masonry Construction Through Natural Aggregate Replacement by Fine Recycled Aggregates in Cement–Lime Mortars

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Abstract: Sustainable development relies on the circularity in the built environment, which, in turn, includes recycling construction and demolition waste and using recycled materials. However, using fine recycled fractions is challenging, especially considering the requirements for new building applications. Yet, producing more widely applied recycled coarse aggregates usually leads to the simultaneous generation of recycled sand fraction, which contains many fines that pose potential problems. This work presents the direct incorporation of concrete and mixed waste-based recycled sand and recycled fines in masonry mortars, on the one hand, as a complete aggregate replacement and, on the other, only replacing the finest aggregate fraction. Such mortars are assessed based on the fresh and hardened mortar properties and are compared to natural aggregate-containing mortars. In the fresh state, the mortars with recycled fines and recycled sand required more mixing water to produce comparable consistency and workability. In a hardened state, mortars with recycled mixed waste sand and fines have demonstrated increased mechanical strength compared to natural aggregate mortars. In contrast, those containing recycled concrete aggregates and fines were inferior in that regard. This indicates the potential of using recycled mixed waste fractions to improve masonry mortar performance, although both types might be important in enhancing the sustainability of masonry construction.

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1. Introduction

Masonry is one of the oldest types of construction, which has withstood the test of time and retained its relevance in the modern world. The most common form of masonry is embodied in walls, often composite structures made from building blocks, such as bricks, joined together by a traditionally cementitious compound known as mortar [1].

Mortars prove their relevance in masonry construction through a variety of distinct applications. Some are used to lay blocks, others as wall renders and plasters, and others have the right properties for restoration and renovation work [2–4]. All masonry mortars generally comprise two main dry ingredients: the binder and the aggregates.

The types and amounts of binding materials usually determine the application of mortars in masonry construction, although aggregates are equally significant, since they provide a structural skeleton in a more environmentally conscious and economically efficient way than binders such as cement, lime, clay, etc. [5,6]. Therefore, fine aggregates

(particle size < 4 mm) are usually the mortar's most voluminous component, often comprising 75% or more by volume of the dry ingredients.

The use of raw mineral deposits for the production of fine aggregates exhausts natural resources, which, over time, causes problems regarding the availability of said minerals, especially in geographical regions where this availability is already limited and highly damaging to the environment [7,8]. Even though some deposits are plentiful, logistical challenges might present unfavourable conditions for the use of such materials, environmentally and economically [9]. On the other hand, principles of circularity in the built environment, reflected upon in the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals [10], strongly rely on the reuse and recycling of materials, such as construction and demolition waste (CDW).

The use of recycled aggregates originating from CDW to replace natural aggregates in new construction materials, mainly concrete, has been proven to decrease the environmental impacts in some instances [11–15]. However, modern sustainability evaluation tools such as life cycle assessment (LCA) suggest that there are various deciding factors when comparing the environmental impacts of recycled aggregates against those of natural aggregates. These factors should encompass recycling processing steps along with the functional performance related to the mechanical properties of products incorporating recycled materials, their durability and serviceability evaluations to achieve a complete and unbiased sustainability assessment, which is why using recycled materials alone does not constitute an automatically sustainable option [11,12]. Taking that into consideration, worldwide experience shows the possible environmental benefits arising from the use of recycled aggregates [13–15]. It is generally agreed that the aggregates present a relatively low environmental impact compared to cement production, thus limiting the extent of potential benefits of substituting them with recycled alternatives [11,12]. Furthermore, the transportation of recycled aggregates is frequently noted as a major contributor to their overall impact [11–15], which might negatively influence some impact categories, such as global warming potential. On the other hand, without proper utilisation, recycled aggregates remain a waste that needs to be landfilled, so their use presents clear benefits regarding land occupation, preservation of natural resources, and potentially other impact categories related to human health and ecosystem quality [11,12,15].

Academic and industrial efforts have led to the legally permitted and regulated use of recycled building materials in cementitious compounds and concrete, further securing their place in the construction materials market [16,17]. This further cements the need for the whole utilisation of recycled aggregates, including recycled fine fractions, which are among the major substitutes for natural sand used in mortars [18,19]. Therefore, there is evidence that recycled-material-incorporating mortars can become a more sustainable alternative to virgin aggregate mortars [20].

Masonry mortars might be suitable recipients for the fine recycled aggregates because they are often not imposed with stringent structural performance requirements [21]. Nonetheless, using recycled materials should not significantly diminish the performance of mortars in masonry construction, as the balance between cost, environmental impact, and performance is sought after. Furthermore, fine recycled aggregates are particularly high in content of particles <250 µm (referred to as "fines" in this work), which are far more challenging to utilise in new construction due to their inherent adverse properties, such as high porosity and water absorption, especially compared to recycled coarse aggregates [22,23]. Therefore, recycled fine aggregates require a suitable application. Substantial research efforts have been dedicated to exploring the possibilities of using recycled fine aggregates in mortars in the 21st century.

As presented in a recently published review, numerous studies have been conducted on using fine recycled aggregates in masonry mortars [24]. However, while some general consensus exists on the effects of using such materials, many factors, including the aggregate origin, type, and the way of incorporation, affect the performance of recycled aggregate mortars.

The higher proportion of relevant literature revolves around incorporating recycled fine aggregates (0–4 mm size range according to EN 13139 [25]) in partial or full replacement of natural sand in mortars for masonry [26–38]. With plenty of studied binder systems, different recycled materials, and raw aggregate replacement levels, scientific agreement and certainty on the effects of recycled materials on masonry mortars are hardly achievable [24]. In all the cases, recycled fine aggregates have been shown to increase the water demand of mortars due to their inherent porosity. However, this did not negatively impact the fresh-state properties of mortars. The decreases in bulk densities and workable life or increases in air content and water retention were not deemed detrimental to the workability of the mortar in laboratory-scale studies. However, the hardened mortar properties were impacted rather significantly. Higher-strength mortars (above 10 MPa compressive strength at 28 days) for masonry were negatively affected in terms of their hardened performance in a number of studies [26,28,29,31,33], whereas some reported increased strength results [29,32]. Lower-strength mortars, on the other hand, were more receptive to the recycled aggregates, with partial natural aggregate replacement formulations often demonstrating increased strength [27,30,35–38], although the opposite effects were also recorded [34,36]. Other common traits included increased shrinkage, water absorption, and porosity [26,28–31,33,34,36–38]. Attributing recycled aggregate mortar performance to a particular type of recycled aggregates has proven difficult, with high variability among the results. However, on average, recycled concrete aggregates were better than recycled masonry or recycled mixed aggregates, but the latter types were also studied less [24].

The use of recycled fines in masonry mortars as fillers has been the topic of some research [39–43]. The standard size definition of fines or fillers is particles below 0.063 mm [25], although fractions <0.125 mm can also be considered part of the filler [17], but, due to variable definitions in the literature, fines and fillers described in this work are materials <0.250 mm. Even though this size range forms part of the fine recycled aggregate composition, fines are considered superfluous in recycled material applications. Yet, in masonry mortars, they can act as filler material, which can increase the cohesiveness of the fresh mortar and potentially modify the hydration or carbonation of the binder. The studies have noted effects, opposite to those of fine recycled aggregates, on fresh mortar behaviour; incremental additions of recycled fines decreased the water demand for similar workability of mortars, which resulted in mortars with increased bulk density [39–42]. Despite that, one of the studies found entrained air content to be similar and slightly declining with the increase in recycled mixed fines content [42], whereas another one has demonstrated that both recycled concrete fines and recycled mixed fines significantly increased the air content of a fresh mortar [40]. The denser fresh mortar matrix translated into improved mechanical strength, although with an increased drying shrinkage [39–42], but decreased capillary water absorption coefficient [39,40,42]. These studies have attributed the improvements in fresh and hardened mortar behaviour to the filler effect of the recycled fines.

In contrast to the recycled fines, the utilisation of recycled fine aggregates in masonry mortars had some drawbacks. Despite that, most previous works have deemed them an acceptable alternative to natural aggregates. Even though most research has dealt with the determination of mortar-scale properties in the laboratory, some studies have focused on the particular application of said mortars and the most prevalent suggestions for recycled aggregate use are in the range of 20–50% replacement of natural aggregates. Recycled fines

used as fillers were explored to a lesser extent, but their effect was most acceptable in the 10–20% replacement range.

The main objective of the current work is to explore the possibilities of incorporating real construction and demolition waste into modern masonry mortars. This provides the basis for feasibility assessment connected with desirable mortar properties, which is very relevant for masonry mortar manufacturers.

This study examines recycled materials processed in Belgium, which, in a typical European context, are sourced from either concrete or mixed waste. A systematic testing approach is employed to differentiate between the recycled materials and, more importantly, to evaluate their performance in masonry mortars. This study considers recycled aggregates as part of the inert mortar fraction and analyses two main options for replacing natural aggregates: one that focuses solely on fine filler materials below 250 μm and the other that utilises the entire fine aggregate fraction. The comparison of fresh and hardened mortar properties serves as the foundation for decision-making regarding the use of specific recycled materials in various types of mortars.

2. Materials and Methodology

2.1. Binder Materials

Portland-limestone cement CEM II A/L 32.5R (Tarmac, Solihull, UK [44]) was used in equal volumetric proportions with hydrated lime CL 90-S (Lhoist, Limelette, Belgium [45]), completing the 1:1:6 cement/lime/aggregate by volume mortar formulation.

2.2. Aggregates

2.2.1. Natural Aggregates

The natural aggregates used in this research were custom-tailored granulometry silicious sand with a particle size distribution conforming to the limits set out by European Standard EN 13139 [25] and British Standard BS 1199 and 1200 [46]. This custom particle size distribution is represented using a dark red curve in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Fine aggregate grading curve and limits adhered to in this study. The area separated by the dark blue line highlights the finest particle region.

2.2.2. Recycled Aggregates

Recycled concrete and recycled mixed aggregates used in this research were obtained from a construction and demolition waste recycling facility in Belgium. Recycled concrete aggregates were produced by selectively crushing structural and nonstructural concrete-based elements of demolished buildings and infrastructure, whereas recycled

mixed aggregates contained a mixture of construction materials in accordance with the Belgian regulation PTV 406 [47]. The compositions of recycled aggregate fractions comply with the limits presented in Table 1.

Table 1. Recycled aggregate constituents and composition limits for recycled concrete and recycled mixed aggregates [47].

Component	Description of the Component	Percentage Range	
		Recycled Concrete Aggregates	Recycled Mixed Aggregates
1	Concrete and concrete products, mortar, concrete masonry units	≥ 70	Not required
2	Unbound aggregates, natural stone, and hydraulically bound aggregates	Not specified	
3	Glass	≤ 2	≤ 2
4	Combination of 1, 2, and 3	≥ 90	≥ 50
5	Clay masonry units, calcium silicate masonry units, aerated concrete (non-floating)	≤ 10	≤ 50
6	Bituminous materials	≤ 5	≤ 5
7	Other non-floating components (clay and soil, metals, wood, plastic, rubber, gypsum)	≤ 1	≤ 1
8	Floating components	≤ 5 or ≤ 2	≤ 5

Both types of aggregates were produced in a 0–10 mm range, with further sieving to the maximum particle size of 2 mm in laboratory conditions. The aggregates were also sieved according to the EN 933-1 [48] to separate the fractions of <63 μm , 63–125 μm , 125–250 μm , 250–500 μm , 500–1000 μm , and 1000–2000 μm .

Due to vast differences in the particle size distribution of recycled aggregates compared to tailored natural aggregates, they were reconstituted using the sieved fractions to match the granulometry presented in Figure 1.

Using such granulometry, both fine recycled concrete aggregates and recycled mixed aggregates were tested for their chemical composition using an X-ray fluorescence (XRF) Zetium spectrometer (Malvern Panalytical, Malvern, UK) and a water-carbon analyzer Eltra CW-800 (ELTRA, Haan, Germany). Test samples were obtained by reducing bulk aggregate samples (~20 kg) using a riffle box and then crushed in a ball mill to pass a 63 μm sieve. The results are presented in Table 2. The main differences between these two types of fine recycled aggregates are the higher silica content in mixed aggregates and lower calcium oxide content, along with the lower extent of carbonation and bound water compared to concrete-based recycled sand.

Table 2. Chemical composition of fine recycled aggregates: main oxides, carbon dioxide, and water.

	SiO ₂	CaO	Al ₂ O ₃	MgO	Fe ₂ O ₃	SO ₃	K ₂ O	Na ₂ O	Others	CO ₂	H ₂ O
Recycled Concrete Aggregates	63.19	15.58	3.58	1.66	1.06	0.98	0.82	0.71	0.03	8.42	3.97
Recycled Mixed Aggregates	76.19	7.32	3.92	0.54	1.81	0.65	1.06	0.66	0.02	5.38	2.45

2.2.3. Aggregate Replacement Strategy, Their Properties, and Mortar Mix Design

Two types of replacement were proposed to study the differences between fine recycled aggregates and their utilisation possibilities. Figure 2 illustrates the general approach:

1. Firstly, the natural aggregates were fully replaced by the recycled aggregates of the same particle size distribution. These mortars are called RCAM and RMAM for recycled concrete aggregate mortar and recycled mixed aggregate mortar, respectively.

2. Secondly, only the fine aggregate fraction $<250\ \mu\text{m}$, herein referred to as “fines”, was partially (50%) and wholly (100%) substituted by the recycled aggregates of both origins. The respective mortars are named RCf for recycled concrete fines or RMf for recycled mixed fines, followed by a number representing the replacement percentage.

Figure 2. Graphical representation of the reference mortar and the different ways of replacing siliceous sand.

Based on the abovementioned strategies, 7 different aggregate mixes were studied here. All of these aggregates were compared in terms of bulk density and water absorption (EN 1097-6 [49]), and the results are presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Water absorption and bulk density of all aggregate mixes used in this study. This table uses mortar nomenclature to differentiate between the aggregate mixes.

	REF	RCf50	RCf100	RMf50	RMf100	RCAM	RMAM
Water Absorption (%)	0.2	8.4	10.1	6.2	8.1	11.7	9.8
Bulk Density (kg/m³)	1505	1415	1352	1462	1429	1207	1336

Evidently, recycled fines significantly influenced the increased water absorption of aggregate mixes. To investigate this effect further, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) was performed in a qualitative manner to showcase the structure and morphology of recycled fractions $<250\ \mu\text{m}$. Secondary electron images of samples were taken using Jeol JSM-7600F scanning electron microscope (JEOL Ltd., Akishima, Tokyo, Japan) at $200\times$ magnification to showcase the topography of fine recycled particles. The results are presented in Figure 3. These high-magnification images demonstrate the irregular surfaces of fine recycled particles, which are reflective of their intrinsic porosity. This leads to the high water absorption capacity demonstrated in Table 3.

Mortars were made according to the mix design outlined in Table 4. The mixing water amount was variable to achieve a consistent flow value of $\sim 175\ \text{mm}$ and comparable fresh-state behaviour overall, which the authors evaluated qualitatively. The criteria for such evaluation included cohesiveness of the mixture, lack of visible bleeding and segregation, and ease of handling, i.e., using a trowel.

Figure 3. Scanning electron images of recycled concrete fines (a) and recycled mixed fines (b).

Table 4. Mix design of mortars with a lime/cement/aggregate ratio equal to 1:1:6 by volume.

Mortar Type	Mass of Lime (%)	Mass of Cement (%)	Mass of Aggregates (%)	Water-Binder Ratio
REF	4.0	10.0	86.0	1.05
RCf50	4.2	10.5	85.3	1.25
RCf100	4.4	10.9	84.7	1.35
RMf50	4.1	10.2	85.7	1.10
RMf100	4.2	10.4	85.4	1.15
RCAM	4.8	12.1	83.1	1.50
RMAM	4.4	11.0	84.6	1.35

2.3. Fresh Mortar Tests

2.3.1. Consistency by Flow Table

As outlined previously, all mortars were formulated with a water content required to produce a flow of 175 ± 10 mm, tested in accordance with EN 1015-3 [50]. The flow test was performed twice on two different batches of mortars.

2.3.2. Fresh Bulk Density

The fresh bulk density of mortars was tested based on the standard method described in EN 1015-6 [51]. A dedicated batch of freshly mixed mortar was placed into a 1 L container and compacted accordingly. This test was performed on two different batches; the result is the average.

2.3.3. Air Content

Air content in fresh mortars after mixing was determined according to EN 1015-7 [52]. A batch of freshly mixed mortar was placed into a 1 litre container and compacted accordingly. This test was performed on two different batches; the result is the average value.

2.3.4. Water Retention

Water retention assessment of all mortars was performed following the guidelines of EN 459-2 [53]. A portion of freshly mixed mortar from the batches used in previous tests was cast into a circular disc on top of an absorbent paper and the absorbed water content

was measured after five minutes. This test was performed on two different batches, with the average result presented here.

2.4. Hardened Mortar Tests

In order to test the hardened properties of mortars, outlined in this section, standard prismatic specimens were made following the procedure in EN 1015-11 [54]. After mixing, the mortars were placed into $160 \times 40 \times 40$ mm³ moulds in two layers, compacting each with a tampering rod. They were transferred into constant temperature (20 ± 2 °C) and high relative humidity ($95 \pm 5\%$) conditions, demoulded after 2 days, and, after 7 days, were transferred into a 20 ± 2 °C temperature and $65 \pm 5\%$ relative humidity environment until the age of testing.

2.4.1. Mechanical Strength

Flexural and compressive strength tests were performed on mortars in accordance with EN 1015-11 [54] at 7, 28, and 90 days. At each age, 6 mortar prisms were tested. The mortars were loaded at rates achieving flexural or compressive failure between 30 and 60 s from the beginning of load application.

2.4.2. Open Porosity

The open porosity testing was performed on 3 mortar prisms at 90 days of age. This age was chosen to allow sufficient time for the air lime to (partially) carbonate and contribute to the development of mortar structure and strength. The test procedure was adopted from RILEM CPC 11.3 [55] and NBN B 24-213 [56] but modified in the following way:

- The samples were taken directly from the curing environment of 20 °C and 65% relative humidity to be water-saturated under vacuum (around 2 h of high vacuum).
- After 24 h of saturation, the samples were wiped free of surface water and weighed— M_{sat} .
- Then, samples were weighed underwater— M_w .
- Afterwards, the samples were dried to a constant weight (0.1% difference between weighing 24 h apart) at 105 °C and weighed— M_{dry} .
- The open porosity was calculated using Formula (1) and expressed in %.

$$\frac{M_{sat} - M_{dry}}{M_{sat} - M_w} \times 100 \quad (1)$$

2.4.3. Capillary Water Absorption

Capillary water absorption was tested using the EN 1015-18 [57] procedure on mortar samples at 90 days of age. The significant difference with the standard procedure was the lack of using filter paper during the prismatic specimen casting. Three mortar prisms were dried to constant mass at 60 °C and were broken in half, their sides were sealed using self-adhesive butyl aluminium tape, and the broken surface was submerged in a container with a constant water level at ~5–10 mm from the bottom of the sample, supported on two plastic bars. The mass gain of each sample was recorded at 1, 3, 5, 10, 15, 20, 30, 45, 60, 90, 120, 1440, and 5760 min from the beginning of the experiment.

In addition to expressing the results in terms of a capillary water absorption coefficient, approximated as the slope of sample mass gain due to water uptake between 10 and 90 min of the experiment, the full capillary absorption curves are plotted as well.

Furthermore, to elucidate the description of the water uptake behaviour of mortars, a new measure, namely the capillary water absorption capacity, was introduced. It was

based on the experimental data and relates the average mass of absorbed water per mortar mass, as described in Formula (2).

$$\frac{m_w}{m_{dry}} \times 100 \quad (2)$$

where m_w is the mass of water absorbed by capillary action in kg.

m_{dry} is the mass of the dry mortar sample before the test in kg.

It is expressed as percentage %.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Fresh Mortar Properties

As described in Section 2.3.1, all mortars were formulated to achieve a consistency of 175 ± 10 mm. With the water–binder ratios presented in Table 4, all mortars had similar flows, with minimal variations—between 171 mm for RMAM and 176 mm for RCAM—Table 5. However, fresh mortar workability is a complex parameter that cannot solely rely on flow table values, thus remaining very cumbersome to measure [58]. The mortars in this study were comparable based on the authors' qualitative assessment. However, adding both types of recycled fines, or full substitution of natural sand by fine recycled aggregates, yielded more homogeneous mortars with a cohesive structure. Mortars incorporating recycled mixed waste fines and aggregates were comparatively the best to work with in a laboratory environment. Such behaviour could be attributed to several properties of recycled aggregate mixes:

- High water absorption of fine recycled aggregates increased the water demand, which, in turn, could influence the plasticity of the mortar [59,60].
- Furthermore, as water absorption of recycled aggregates is a time-consuming process [61] and due to the presence of recycled fines, the mortars could benefit from eliminating bleeding or water separation due to insufficient hydraulic material for the used water-to-binder (W/B) ratios.
- As confirmed by the high water absorption, highly porous and irregularly shaped particles in recycled aggregates could affect the interparticle interactions and packing in the fresh state, producing a more cohesive mixture.

Table 5. Mortar fresh properties.

Mortar	Flow (mm)	Water Retention (%)	Bulk Density (kg/m ³)	Air Content (%)
REF	174.0	82	2062	4.6
RCf50	173.5	85	1940	5.2
RCf100	172.0	87	1880	5.6
RMf50	174.5	87	2040	5.4
RMf100	176.5	88	1995	5.2
RCAM	176.0	88	1790	6.4
RMAM	171.0	90	1860	5.0

In terms of water retention of the fresh mortar mixes, adding recycled aggregates of both waste types gradually increased the mortar's capacity to retain moisture. However, using the fines was more effective than utilising the whole recycled aggregate particle size range, since the difference between the reference mortar and those with fines is higher than between mortars with fines and RCAM and RMAM. Overall, fine recycled mixed aggregates fared marginally better than their concrete counterparts. Notably, the initially occurring water absorption in the recycled aggregate mixes could not be objectively assessed in the 5 min water retention testing timeframe. The increased water retention of mortars with

recycled aggregates might be deceptive because, throughout the test duration, both the absorptive filter paper and the recycled aggregates compete for the mixing water. In real construction, such competition might prove recycled aggregates inferior due to highly absorbent units, eventually dewatering the mortar and the recycled aggregates, causing uneven or insufficient hydration, shrinkage, and bond formation [62,63].

The bulk density of masonry mortars is a highly significant characteristic, since it determines the raw material consumption and influences mortar performance. A lower bulk density is more favourable, as fewer materials are required to build the same volume of a structure, such as a wall. However, higher material density often indicates better mechanical performance; therefore, a balanced approach is required. In this case, adding recycled fines at 50% and 100% of silicious fine substitution would decrease the bulk density of mortar by ~6% and 9%, respectively. Meanwhile, the full substitution of silicious sand with recycled fine concrete sand of the same granulometry could decrease the bulk density by around 13%. This effect is influenced by the additional mixing water as well as the lower density of recycled aggregates. Although, with recycled mixed fines, the effect was not as pronounced, especially at 50% substitution, which had a W/B ratio similar to the REF mortar.

Another parameter directly connected to bulk density and, therefore, mortar use efficiency is the air content, which was only slightly affected by the use of recycled fines and recycled fine aggregates. The highest difference compared to the reference mortar was observed in the RCAM mix, which had the most porous and least dense recycled concrete aggregates and the highest proportion of water. Despite this, none of the fresh mortars were noted for a high air content. Higher levels of air entrainment, if required, are normally achievable with the help of chemical admixtures.

Overall, the main deciding factor in the fresh mortar formulation is the amount of mixing water, which depends on the type and quantity of fine recycled aggregates or fines.

3.2. Hardened Mortar Properties

3.2.1. Mechanical Strength

The evolution of the studied mortars' mechanical strength was determined over a period starting with the early age (7 d), when cement hydration would prevail due to favourable conditions of high relative humidity curing, continuing on to 28 d, which represents the reference strength classification value for a mortar [21], and exploring later age hydration and carbonation of lime at 90 d [64].

Figures 4 and 5 present the compressive and flexural strength values of all studied mortars. For clarity, the mortars were separated into those containing recycled fines at two replacement levels (Figure 4) and those with complete natural sand replacement by recycled aggregates (Figure 5). The reference mortar values are included in both figures to aid comparison. The values of flexural strength are presented on a comparable scale.

Firstly, the reference mortar has shown a good strength progression with age, reaching 7.2 MPa at 28 days, which fits within the M5 mortar strength class [21], often expected of a 1:1:6 cement–lime masonry mortar. As a benchmark, the 7-day age strength is at ~58% of the 28 d strength, and long-term strength development slowed down, with ~112% of the 28 d compressive strength recorded at 90 days.

The flexural strength of reference mortar seemed to evolve slower in the early stages, reaching ~48% of the 28 d strength at 7 days, although progression from 28 to 90 days was very similar to that of the compressive strength, with a ~10% increase.

Mortars with recycled concrete fines have exhibited a poorer mechanical performance compared to the reference at all ages, which is directly related to the increase in recycled fines in the mix, since RCf100 performed worse than RCf50. The compressive strength of the

RCf mortars was at ~70% of the REF mortar strength at 50% fines' replacement and slightly lower at 100% replacement. Despite this, the age-related progression was on par with the reference mortars. Recycled concrete fines undeniably induced a higher mixing water demand, which at least partly explains the reduction in mechanical strength. However, the quality of the recycled aggregates could also contribute to poorer performance.

Figure 4. Compressive (a) and flexural (b) strength of mortars with recycled fines.

Figure 5. Compressive (a) and flexural (b) strength of mortars with recycled aggregates.

The introduction of recycled mixed waste fines has produced a completely different effect on the mortar strength. In terms of compressive strength, both the RMf50 and RMf100 mortar were around 37–39% stronger at 7 days compared to the reference. At 28 days, some differences between 50% and 100% fines' replacement became apparent, with 36% and 30% increases over the reference, respectively. However, some time after 28 days, the strength evolution reversed, showing increases of 17% for RMf50 and 15% for RMf100 compared to REF mortar. The drop in strength from 28d to 90d was only recorded for the RMf mortars, suggesting that internal-structure-modifying processes took precedence over the theoretical strength gain from the carbonation of lime. Drying shrinkage could be the underlying cause of this.

Interestingly, the progression of flexural strength of RMf50 and RMf100 mortars did not mirror the trend established for compressive strength. The gain in flexural strength was recorded over the three testing ages, and, counterintuitively, the higher dosage of recycled mixed waste fines seemed to improve the bending strength the most, especially at an early age. The explanation of such behaviour is currently lacking, although it might be related to the recycled mixed waste fines' interparticle bonds, which might be favourable for resisting the 3-point bending.

When replacing the natural sand completely by recycled concrete or recycled mixed aggregates, the trends of the compressive-strength-related effects observed in the samples with recycled fines were replicated (Figure 4). Both RCAM and RMAM mortars have demonstrated reduced compressive strength compared to the RCf and RMf mortars. Similarly to the previously discussed cases, the compressive strength of the recycled concrete aggregate mortar was significantly lower compared to the reference mortar, although it followed a similar strength evolution over time. Contrastingly, RMAM surpassed the REF strength at 7 and 28 days of age, but the previously encountered longer-term strength reduction meant it was similar at compressive load resistance at 90 days.

The flexural strength of recycled concrete aggregate mortar was comparable with the reference in the early age, although the REF improved drastically at 28 and 90 days. The RMAM mortar had the highest bending strength at 7 days, with REF catching up at 28 and 90 days, respectively. The flexural strength of both recycled aggregate mortar formulations did not present a clearly identifiable trend compared to the mortars containing only recycled fines, suggesting that the presence of larger recycled aggregate particles of different origins might have a variable effect on the mortar's bending resistance.

Using recycled concrete aggregates, either by fully replacing natural aggregates or only the finest fraction, is detrimental to the compressive strength. RCAM and RCf100 mortars cannot satisfy the condition of 5 MPa minimum strength at 28 days for the M5 classification, which complicates this comparison. On one hand, reduction in strength is not desirable, but it is influenced by the higher required amount of mixing water, which also influences the consumption of such mortar, based on the decreased bulk density. Such issues are omitted by substituting natural sand with recycled mixed aggregates or fines. However, it comes with uncertainty regarding long-term performance, which was not tested in this study.

3.2.2. Capillary Water Absorption

The water transport properties of mortars are an important characteristic of masonry construction, since they can act in both beneficial and detrimental ways, impacting the longevity, safety, and comfort of buildings and people [65–67].

Each application case requires a mortar with certain water transport properties related to the microstructure of different mortar formulations.

Figure 6 presents the results of the studied mortars' capillary water absorption. Furthermore, Table 6 shows the capillary water absorption coefficient according to EN 1015-18 and the water absorption capacity defined in this work.

Table 6. Mortar capillary water absorption coefficient and water absorption capacity results. Standard errors in parentheses.

	REF	RCf50	RCf100	RMf50	RMf100	RCAM	RMAM
Capillary Water Absorption Coefficient (kg/(m ² min ^{0.5}))	1.23 (0.04)	1.36 (0.05)	1.41 (0.09)	1.06 (0.06)	1.00 (0.06)	1.73 (0.10)	0.94 (0.09)
Capillary Water Absorption Capacity (%)	12.37 (0.23)	15.61 (0.27)	17.29 (0.54)	13.56 (0.33)	14.34 (0.19)	19.87 (0.41)	16.63 (0.56)

The use of recycled concrete fines as a partial or complete substitute for the silicious fines does not significantly affect the initial stages of water absorption in the 1:1:6 cement–lime mortars, when compared against the natural aggregate mortar (Figure 6a). This is also reflected in the water absorption coefficient presented in Table 6, since the coefficient is the slope between two measurement points at 10 and 90 min from the initial immersion of the sample. However, it is the later age when the differences between the recycled concrete

finer and natural aggregates become more apparent. The higher water absorption of recycled fines influences the water absorption capacity of the hardened mortar, substantially increasing it as demonstrated in Table 6. The trend continues with the further increase in recycled concrete aggregate content—RCAM in Figure 6b and Table 6.

Figure 6. Capillary water absorption of mortars with recycled fines (a) and mortars with recycled aggregates (b).

Recycled mixed waste fines present a modified water uptake compared to the silicious fines. Initially, the capillary water absorption is slower, resulting in a gentle slope and lower water absorption coefficient (Figure 6a and Table 6). However, similarly to the recycled concrete fines, the water absorption capacity is higher than that of the reference sand, and RMf samples reach a plateau later than RCf and REF mortars, indicating a significantly slower water uptake. The slowing trend is reflected in the behaviour of RMAM (Figure 6b), whereas the water absorption capacity of the hardened mortar increases, in line with the initial water absorption capacity of the aggregates (Tables 3 and 6).

As evident from the graphical representation in Figure 6, considering not only the water absorption coefficient during the first 90 min but also the full extent of the water absorption behaviour is crucial in the analysis of recycled aggregates. The early-stage water uptake can be useful in relating this mortar property to real-world scenarios with limited exposure to water (e.g., light, occasional rain). In contrast, the water absorption capacity is better correlated with high moisture saturation conditions, especially concerning material durability.

3.2.3. Porosity

The porosity of mortars is tied directly to the other hardened mortar properties, including the aforementioned capillary water absorption and mechanical strength. However, porosity evaluation might be dependent on the particular testing method. In the case of this study, the water saturation under vacuum and subsequent drying at 105 degrees Celsius might harm the microstructure by partially destroying the temperature-sensitive hydrated phases, such as ettringite [68].

The results of the open porosity testing on mortars at 90 days of age are presented in Table 7. The open porosity of the reference mortar appears to be the lowest at slightly below 27%. The closest and least porous hardened mortars are RMf50 and RMf100, mixed using the least mixing water compared to other recycled mortars. RCf50 and RCf100 mortars demonstrate higher porosities at 33% and 35%, whereas the highest porosity is recorded for the RCAM at ~40% and RMAM at ~37%.

Table 7. Open porosities of mortars. Standard errors in parentheses.

	REF	RCf50	RCf100	RMf50	RMf100	RCAM	RMAM
Open Porosity (%)	26.83 (0.21)	33.05 (0.14)	35.01 (0.35)	29.13 (0.22)	29.96 (0.17)	40.32 (0.33)	36.87 (0.40)

Recycled concrete fines have a more significant effect on the mortar porosity than recycled mixed fines. Still, it relates to the extra mixing water in the fresh mortar mixture. However, the difference between RMf100 and RMAM suggests that the extra water and the inclusion of larger-sized recycled mixed aggregates increase the porosity more than just replacing siliceous filler with recycled fines.

The demonstration of higher porosities hinders the explanation of the superior strength of recycled mixed aggregate mortars. However, as mentioned previously, the open porosity testing implemented in this study does not allow for considerations of the potential structural phases that decompose at temperatures lower than 105 °C.

3.3. Comparative Analysis

Even though individual fresh and hardened mortar properties provide some basis for describing and comparing mortars, it has been demonstrated throughout this work that these properties are interconnected. Therefore, for a complete analysis of mortar-scale performance, a systematic approach, designed to help evaluate mortars based on particular expectations, is required nevertheless.

In this study, a grouping of all tested mortar properties was conducted through radar plots with individual scales for each of the nine properties. The result is showcased in Figure 7. Both parts of the figure are made to be interpreted starting from the W/B ratio and going clockwise. This also represents the testing sequence of fresh and hardened properties.

Figure 7. Radar plots of the tested mortar properties: (a) mortars with recycled fines; (b) mortars with recycled aggregates. Flexural and compressive strength values correspond to 28d tests. Scale is relative; REF values always equal 1.00.

The radar plots utilised in this section can help visualise and interpret the results of mortar scale testing. Furthermore, some properties are very use-case-dependent and, by selecting the relevant properties and/or separating the different mortar states, it is possible to compare different mortars to find optimal solutions directly.

In the case of partial substitution of natural aggregates by recycled concrete fines, the following sequence of events can be constructed (Figure 7a):

- More mixing water is required to achieve the targeted mortar consistency;
- The bulk density decreases due to extra water and lighter aggregate fraction;
- Air content increases slightly;
- Water retention slightly increases due to continued water absorption by the fines;
- In a hardened state, the flexural and compressive strength decreases significantly;
- Capillary water absorption coefficient and capacity increases;
- Porosity increases.

These effects are amplified by introducing even more fines (RCf100 vs. RCf50) into the mix.

Similarly to the fines, the full natural sand replacement by fine recycled concrete aggregates exaggerates the observed effects further—Figure 7b. The only exception is the flexural strength of RCAM mortar, which lies in between those of RCf50 and RCf100 but well below REF.

Recycled mixed fines induce completely different changes in a 1:1:6 mortar compared to the concrete fines. The modifications in relation to the reference mortar are:

- A slightly higher amount of mixing water is required to produce mortars with similar consistency;
- Bulk density decrease is marginal;
- The air content slightly increases;
- Water retention somewhat improves;
- In the hardened state, both flexural and compressive strengths are increased. RMf50 is lower in bending strength than RMf100 but higher in compressive strength;
- Capillary water absorption coefficient decreases;
- Capillary water absorption capacity increases;
- Porosity increases.

The further addition of mixed fines amplifies these effects unless stated otherwise.

As per Figure 7b, the recycled mixed waste aggregate mortars RMAM present further increases in W/B ratio, water retention, capillary water absorption capacity, and porosity. Consequently, the bulk density decreases but air content remains similar. The mechanical strength, while surpassing that of a reference mortar at 28 days, decreases with further age and, in Section 3.2.1., it was demonstrated to decrease below the reference level at 90 days.

4. Conclusions

This study has explored two distinct natural aggregate replacement scenarios using two types of recycled materials and three levels of recycled aggregate incorporation. The findings of this work can be summarised in the following way:

- Recycled concrete and recycled mixed aggregates, including their finest fractions, induce higher water demand due to their high water absorption. This can be viewed as a negative aspect, due to increased water use and/or the need to use additives.
- The resulting mortars are similar in terms of their fresh performance, although the increased water content and the use of lower-density aggregates result in lower-density mortars, which can be favourable considering material expenditures in masonry applications.
- Recycled concrete fines diminish hardened mortar performance, the severity of which depends on the proportion of recycled fines. Such an effect could be disadvantageous in applications where hardened properties are of primary importance.
- Recycled concrete aggregates used in full substitution of siliceous aggregates enable the production of the lightest and most water-demanding mortars with the worst

mechanical properties in this study. In cases where mechanical performance decrease can be tolerated, the weight savings could be favourable.

- Recycled mixed fines, on the other hand, improve the strength of mortars, although the improvement is not sustained over time. This improvement allows lowering the binder content to achieve the required performance.
- Recycled mixed aggregates also show early-age and 28-day improvement of mechanical strength, which declines towards 90 days of age.
- The use of recycled concrete aggregates hastens and increases the water absorption behaviour of mortars. In contrast, those made with recycled mixed aggregates absorb water slower, yet to a larger extent than natural aggregate mortars.
- The open porosity of recycled masonry mortars tends to increase with increased recycled material content.
- Mortar properties can be assessed, interpreted, and correlated holistically, depending on the scope of use-case requirements. Such flexibility offers prioritisation of particular properties, making recycled materials more accessible for practical use cases.

The scope of this work is strictly limited to mortar-scale properties and testing methods, which might present challenges in the broader context of the research. Other limitations, such as the particularity of recycled aggregates, selection of mix design, and subjective material assessments used in this study, must also be acknowledged.

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